

Optimizing Smart Grid Resilience

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Abstract—Power systems are prone to cascading outages. However, considering only a sub-set of these constraints leading to large-scale blackouts. Intentional controlled islanding allows a set of feasible candidate islanding solutions to be (ICI) is an effective corrective control action that limits the consequences of these catastrophic events by splitting the system into smaller sustainable islands. This paper proposes an ICI algorithm based on an exact Mixed Integer Programming Formulation (MILP) that directly determines an islanding solution with minimal power-flow disruption for any given number of islands, while ensuring that each island contains only coherent generators. In addition, the proposed algorithm enables operators to constrain any transmission line to be excluded from the solution, allows the control of the size of islands and ensures their connectivity. To reduce the search space of the MILP and the overall complexity of the problem, a preprocessing procedure that finds the trees which connect the generators of each coherent group with the minimum number of nodes is also presented. The exact ICI algorithm is tested using dynamic models of the IEEE 39- and IEEE 118-Bus test systems. Multiple case studies are developed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the algorithm to different system conditions.

splitting

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical power systems occasionally experience cascading outages leading to large-scale blackouts. Intentional controlled islanding (ICI), also called system splitting or controlled system separation, is an effective corrective control action to mitigate these catastrophic events [1]. ICI can be used as a final resort to save the system from a partial or a complete blackout. When the system is subject to a severe disturbance and the conventional control systems are unable to keep the system stable, ICI can determine in realtime (within a few seconds in practice) a set of branches to be disconnected across the grid to create smaller sustainable and stable subsystems, also known as *islands* [2, 3].

When determining this set of branches, multiple constraints, such as generator coherency, load-generation balance, transmission line availability, thermal limits, and voltage and transient stability should be considered. In general, it would be too complicated to find a real-time solution that satisfies all these constraints, or even confirm if such a solution exists. In addition, the combinatorial explosion of the solution space that occurs for large power systems increases the complexity of

produced. The exclusion of some constraints means that solving the problem [2]. additional corrective measures [1, 4] are necessary to ensure that each island retains its stability in the post-islanding stage.

Among the aforementioned constraints, the generator coherency constraint is crucial for the success of the controlled separation, as it enhances the transient stability of the islands [2, 4]. Hence, current approaches for ICI aim to split the system such that each island contains only coherent generators [2-8].

In these approaches, the ICI is modeled as a combinatorial optimization problem, whose two main types of objective function are *minimal power-flow disruption* and *minimal power imbalance* within islands. The *power-flow disruption* is expressed by the arithmetic sum of active power in each disconnected transmission line. Methods for minimal powerflow disruption minimize the change of the power flow pattern within the system following system splitting [8]. On the other hand, the *power imbalance* is expressed by the algebraic sum of active power on each disconnected transmission line (considering the direction of power flow). Approaches for finding islanding solutions with minimal power imbalance minimize the load-generation imbalance within the formed islands [12].

Even though these approaches result in different islanding solutions, they both can be described as searching problems on graphs, which are generally *NP-hard* [11]. In other words, there is no general polynomial time algorithm to find the optimal solution. Hence, to overcome this problem, computationally more efficient algorithms that approximate the optimal solution must be used instead [3-5]. In particular, solutions with minimal power flow disruption can be achieved using efficient graph theoretic techniques such as spectral clustering. This technique uses the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of a matrix associated with a graph that represents the power system to determine splitting solutions within polynomial time. Spectral Clustering is used in [2], where a Spectral Clustering Controlled Islanding (SCCI) algorithm has been proposed to minimize the power-flow disruption, while ensuring that each island contains only coherent generators. However, an islanding solution can only

be directly determined when the number of islands is two, i.e., the SCCI algorithm only finds a solution for the bisection case. This issue is resolved by applying recursive bisection [2]. Nevertheless, recursive bisection is a computationally demanding technique that requires the repeated eigendecomposition of a matrix associated with the graph. Recursive bisection can also affect the quality of the islanding solution [9]; better solutions may be missed.

An exact Mixed Integer Linear Programming formulation (MILP) approach for the building partitioning problem has been proposed in [10]. The MILP formulation is based on graph decomposition approaches and partitions the building into smaller sections. The building is transformed into a graph which is partitioned into subgraphs, indicating the group of rooms in each section while ensuring (i) maximum decoupling between the various subgraphs, (ii) strong connectivity between the rooms of a subgraph, and (iii) control of the number of allocated rooms in each subgraph. Due to its easily adaptable constraints, the aforementioned algorithm can easily be applied to other applications. Therefore, an application of the exact MILP formulation on power systems for solving effectively the ICI problem is presented in this paper. Specifically, this paper proposes an exact ICI algorithm that directly determines an islanding solution with minimal power-flow disruption for any given number of islands, while ensuring that each island contains only coherent generators. Additionally, it enables operators to constrain any transmission line to be excluded from the solution (e.g., transformers), allows the control of the size of islands and ensures that each resulting island is connected. It is noted that, due to the high adaptability of the MILP formulation, more constraints can be easily incorporated. Crucially, this paper also proposes a preprocessing procedure which finds the trees that connect the generators of each coherent group with the minimum number of nodes. The nodes of these trees are assigned to specific islands through additional constraints to the MILP formulation for reducing its search space, and therefore, the overall complexity of the problem. The exact ICI algorithm is tested using dynamic models of the IEEE 39- and IEEE 118-Bus test systems. Simulation results are used to demonstrate the effectiveness and the computational efficiency of the proposed algorithm.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the background material on graph theory, and explains the proposed exact ICI algorithm along with the preprocessing procedure. Simulation results based on IEEE 39- and IEEE 118-Bus test systems are presented in Section III. The paper concludes in Section IV.

II. INTENTIONAL CONTROLLED ISLANDING

This section presents an application of the exact MILP formulation to solve the ICI problem for minimal power-flow disruption. The graph theory fundamentals are also given in this section.

A. Graph Theory Fundamentals

In graph theory, an undirected graph-model $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ can be used to describe an m -generator and n -bus power system. In this graph-model, the node set $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ denotes the buses while the edge set \mathcal{E} with elements $e_{ij} = (v_i, v_j), i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ denotes the transmission lines. The set \mathcal{V}^{gen} is a subset of the node set \mathcal{V} that contains only those buses with generators directly connected to them. The set \mathcal{W} , with elements $w_{ij} = (v_i, v_j), i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, is a set of edge weights representing the weight factors (power flow) associated with the transmission lines.

A *cutset* \mathcal{E}_S is the set of edges to be removed to split into $k, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ subgraphs \mathcal{G}_k with node sets V_1, \dots, V_k . For the case of two islands, the sum of the weights of the edges within this cutset \mathcal{E}_S is called the cut, which is defined as in equation (1).

$$\text{cut}(V_1, V_2) = \sum_{i \in V_1, j \in V_2} w_{ij} \quad (1)$$

In the ICI problem for minimal power-flow disruption, \mathcal{E}_S consists of the edges that represent the transmission lines in the system to be disconnected to create the islands. The value of the cut corresponds to the power-flow disruption in the resulting island.

B. Exact ICI Algorithm for Minimal Power-Flow Disruption

The ICI problem for solving the minimal power-flow disruption can be represented as a constrained combinatorial optimization, with the objective function,

$$\min_{\mathcal{E}_S} \sum_{i,j \in \mathcal{V}} |P_{ij}| + |P_{ji}| \quad \text{st. } \mathcal{V}^{gen} \cap \mathcal{V}_S = \emptyset, \mathcal{E}_C \cap \mathcal{E}_S = \emptyset \quad (2)$$

where P_{ij} and P_{ji} represent the active power flow in the branch from bus i to j , and from j to i , respectively (to accommodate network losses). \mathcal{E}_C is an edge subset that contains all the branches that cannot be disconnected (e.g., transformers, critical lines). The use of minimal power-flow disruption as the objective function minimizes the sum of the absolute values of the active power exchange between islands. This property improves the transient stability of the formed islands, reduces the possibility of overloading the transmission lines within the newly created islands and makes islands resynchronization

easier [12], [13]. The constraints applied when satisfying this objective function deal with coherent generator groups and line availability.

1) MILP formulation to solve the ICI problem

Consider an undirected, connected graph $G = (V, E)$ and a matrix $W = [w_{ij}]$ for the edge weights $w_{ij}, (i, j) \in E$, with $w_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^+$. The objective is to partition the graph into k subgraphs indicating the islands while a) minimizing the weight of the edges that are not included in any subgraph which is defined as the partitioning cost and is described by the objective function:

$$\text{Partitioning Cost} = \min_{z_{ij} \in \{0,1\}} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} 2(1 - z_{ij})w_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

b) controlling the size of islands and c) ensuring that each produced subgraph is connected. In addition, the resulting

subgraphs $G_h = (V_h, E_h)$ where $V_h \subseteq V$ and $E_h \subseteq E$ and $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, k\}$, must follow a minimum cardinality restriction as $|V_h| \leq M_h$ where $M_h \in \mathbb{N}$. Variables $z_{ij}, (i, j) \in E$ are defined as the decision variables where $z_{ij} = 1$ if the edge is included in any island and $z_{ij} = 0$ otherwise. It is noted that a detailed description of the aforementioned MILP formulation can be found in [10].

C. Preprocessing Procedure

Since the MILP formulation allows the easy manipulation of its existing constraints, a preprocessing procedure is developed for reducing the search space of the MILP and the overall complexity of the problem. The preprocessing procedure has as inputs i) the graph

$G = (V, E)$ of the power system with all weights equal to one and ii) a set $\{V_h^{gen}, E_h^{gen}\}_{h \in \mathcal{K}}$, with $V_h^{gen} \subseteq V$ which holds the coherent generator groups for each island G_h to be formed. The objective of the preprocessing procedure is to find a tree $T_h \subseteq (V_h, E_h)$ in G for each island with minimum number of nodes, spanning to all generator nodes in each V_h^{gen} . Therefore, the nodes that are included in T_h will be directly assigned to their resulting island in the MILP formulation, ensuring the generator coherency. It is noted that in the case where a tree $T_h \subseteq (V_h, E_h)$ does not contain any load-bus (e.g., a coherent group that consists of only one generator), then the particular tree is expanded to include one through finding the minimum path between them. This adjustment avoids the production of isolated generator nodes, and consequently, more reliable islands are formed. The problem of connecting a set of nodes in a graph with the minimum tree is the minimum Steiner problem in graphs which is a well-known NP-complete problem [11]. Therefore, in time depended applications, approximation algorithms are more suitable. The proposed preprocessing procedure consists of a simple approximation of the Steiner problem in graphs that utilizes the shortest path

algorithm, Dijkstra. Note that, providing an approximation for the Steiner problem in graphs is not the main objective of this paper. The preprocessing procedure is as in the next column.

The preprocessing procedure addresses each generator group individually and can be separated in two sections. In the first section (lines 1-8 of preprocessing procedure), the objective is to form trees that include at least two generator vertices from set V_h^{gen} . At the end of the first section, the generated unconnected trees $\{T_h^{(m)}, E_h^{(m)}\}_{m \in \mathcal{M}}$, $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$ include all the generator nodes. However, the final solution should be a unified tree that consists of all the smaller trees. Therefore, in the second section (lines 9-18), all the individual trees are connected together using the smallest

Preprocessing procedure:

- $$h \in \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{V}_h = \emptyset$$
- 1: **While** $\mathcal{V}_h^{gen} \subsetneq \mathcal{V}_h$ **do**
 - 2: **For all** $i \in \mathcal{V}_h^{gen}$
 Find the minimum path
 - 3: $\mathcal{P}_{i,j} = (\mathcal{V}_{i,j}, \mathcal{E}_{i,j}), \forall j \in \mathcal{V}_h^{gen}, j \notin \mathcal{V}_h$ in \mathcal{G} using Dijkstra
 - 4: $\mathcal{P}_i^{min} = \min_j \{\mathcal{P}_{i,j}\}$
 - 5: **End For**
 - 6: $\mathcal{P}^* = \min_{i \in \mathcal{V}_h^{gen}} \{\mathcal{P}_i^{min}\}$
 - 7: $\mathcal{V}_h = \mathcal{V}_h \cup \mathcal{V}^*, \mathcal{E}_h = \mathcal{E}_h \cup \mathcal{E}^*$, where \mathcal{V}^* and \mathcal{E}^* correspond to the vertices and edges of \mathcal{P}^* respectively
 - 8: **End While**
- At this point, \mathcal{T}_h may not be connected. In such a case, \mathcal{T}_h consists of $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, m\}$ individual trees $\mathcal{T}_h^{(m)} = (\mathcal{V}_h^{(m)}, \mathcal{E}_h^{(m)})$.
- 9: $\mathcal{G}' = (\mathcal{V}', \mathcal{E}') = \mathcal{G}$
 - 10: **While** \mathcal{T}_h is not connected **do**
 - 11: $\mathcal{E}' = \mathcal{E}' \setminus \mathcal{E}_h$
 - 12: **For all** $i \in \mathcal{V}_h^{(m)}, m \in \mathcal{M}$
 Find the minimum path
 - 13: $\mathcal{P}_{i,j} = (\mathcal{V}_{i,j}, \mathcal{E}_{i,j}), \forall j \in \mathcal{V}_h^{(q)}, q \in \mathcal{M}, q \neq m$ in \mathcal{G}' using Dijkstra
 - 14: $\mathcal{P}_i^{min} = \min_j \{\mathcal{P}_{i,j}\}$
 - 15: **End For**
 - 16: $\mathcal{P}^* = \min_{i \in \mathcal{V}_h^{(m)}} \{\mathcal{P}_i^{min}\}$
 - 17: $\mathcal{V}_h = \mathcal{V}_h \cup \mathcal{V}^*, \mathcal{E}_h = \mathcal{E}_h \cup \mathcal{E}^*$, where \mathcal{V}^* and \mathcal{E}^* correspond to the vertices and edges of \mathcal{P}^* respectively
 - 18: **End While**

paths between them to form the final tree $\mathcal{T}_h \supseteq \bigcup_m \mathcal{T}_h^{(m)}$ that connects all the generator vertices \mathcal{V}_h^{gen} . Note that the preprocessing procedure can be executed simultaneously for all the generator groups.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the aforementioned exact ICI algorithm, the IEEE 39-Bus and 118-Bus test systems are used. The dynamic data of the generators and the details of the controllers (i.e., AVR and governors) can be found in [14]. The algorithm is aimed to be used following the determination of the necessity to split the power system. All times quoted are based upon simulations performed in Matlab (a PC with 3.10 GHz dual core CPU and 4 GB RAM).

A. IEEE 39-Bus Test System

The single-line diagram of the IEEE 39-Bus test system is presented in Fig. 3. This system has 10 synchronous generators,

34 transmission lines, 12 transformers and 19 constant power loads.

1) Case Study I

Testing case description: At time $t = 1$ s, both ends of transmission line 17-27 are opened. As a result, a transient instability is created into the system. Based on a two-step methodology proposed in [15] for real-time identification of coherent generator groups, for the case of two islands ($k=2$), the coherent generator groups are $\{G30, G37, G38, G39\}$ and $\{G31, G32, G33, G34, G35, G36\}$. The necessity to split the system is considered to be at 2 s. Hence, considering the power flow and actual topology of the system at $t = 2$ s, the proposed exact ICI algorithm is used to find the optimal islanding solution. As mentioned in Section II, the preprocessing procedure finds first the trees which connect all the generators of each coherent group with the minimum number of nodes (Fig. 1). The nodes of these trees are then served as an additional constraint to the MILP formulation. The implementation of the ICI algorithm identifies the optimal solution (for minimum imbalance) across the lines 8-9, 3-4 and 3-18 (red dashed line in Fig. 3). The solution was found in approximately 0.043 s. Hence, islanding was undertaken at $t = 2.043$ s.

For $k=3$, the coherent generator groups obtained are $\{G30, G37, G38, G39\}$, $\{G31, G32\}$ and $\{G33, G34, G35, G36\}$ [15]. Fig. 2 shows the trees found by the preprocessing procedure. The islanding solution determined by the execution of the exact ICI algorithm is marked in Fig. 3 (blue dotted line). This solution was obtained in approximately

Figure 1. Case Study I: Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 39-Bus test system for $k=2$

Figure 2. Case Study I: Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 39-Bus test system for $k=3$

Figure 3. Case Study I: Single-line diagram of IEEE 39-Bus test system with optimal islanding solution for $k=2$ and $k=3$

0.041 s and thus the corresponding corrective controlled strategy was undertaken at $t = 2.041$ s. Table I summarizes the islanding solution and the value of the cut (eq. 1) for each case. It is important to note that there are a few seconds for controlled islanding after the system suffers a severe fault [6]. Consequently, it can be seen that the proposed ICI algorithm can meet the requirement of real-time controlled islanding.

TABLE I
EXACT ISLANDING SOLUTIONS FOR THE IEEE-39 BUS TEST SYSTEM
(CASE STUDY I)

No. of Islands (k)	Cutset	Cut (MW)	Time (s)
	8-9, 3-4, 3-18	173.078	0.043
	8-9, 3-4, 3-18, 14-15	173.932	0.041

Figure 4. Case Study II: Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 39-Bus test system for $k=2$

Figure 5. Case Study II: Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 39-Bus test system for $k=3$

Figure 6. Case Study II: Single-line diagram of IEEE 39-Bus test system with optimal islanding solution for $k=2$ and $k=3$

2) Case Study II

Testing case description: At time $t = 1$ s, the value of loads at buses 3, 4, 7, and 8 is increased by 10% (total step change of 157.78 MW). For $k=2$, the coherent generator groups obtained are $\{G31, G32\}$ and $\{G30, G33, G34, G35, G36, G37, G38, G39\}$ while for $k=3$ the $\{G39\}$, $\{G31, G32\}$ and $\{G30, G33, G34, G35, G36, G37, G38\}$ [15]. The necessity to split the system is considered to be at 2 s. For these cases, the trees found by the preprocessing procedure connecting the generators of each coherent group with the minimum number of nodes are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively. Here, it is important to mention that for the case of three islands, an adjustment has been made in order to ensure that at least one load will be assigned to the island including only G1 (i.e., load 39). Hence, no isolated generator nodes are produced. Considering the power flow and actual topology of the system at $t = 2$ s, the islanding solutions determined by the execution of the exact ICI algorithm for both cases are marked in Fig. 6 and summarized in Table II.

TABLE II
EXACT ISLANDING SOLUTIONS FOR THE IEEE-39 BUS TEST SYSTEM
(CASE STUDY II)

No. of Islands (k)	Cutset	Cut (MW)	Time (s)

	8-9, 3-4, 14-15	192.080	0.042
	8-9, 3-4, 14-15, 1-39	319.994	0.051

B. IEEE 118-Bus Test System

The second test system used to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed ICI algorithm is the IEEE 118-Bus test system. The topology of the system is shown in Fig. 10. This test system contains 19 synchronous generators, 177 transmission lines, 9 transformers and 91 constant power loads. The coherent groups of generator of the IEEE 118-Bus test system are obtained by using the coherency algorithm [16] for up to four groups (Table III). Figs. 7-9 show the trees found by the preprocessing procedure for each case. As mentioned above, the nodes of these trees will be served as an additional constraint to the MILP formulation which will contribute to the reduction of its search space. It is noted that

TABLE III

COHERENT GENERATOR GROUPS FOR THE IEEE 118-BUS TEST SYSTEM

No. of Islands (<i>k</i>)	Coherent Generator Groups
	{10, 12, 25, 26, 31} {46, 49, 54, 61, 65, 66, 69, 80, 87, 89, 100, 103, 111 }
	{10, 12, 25, 26, 31}, {46, 49, 54, 59, 61, 65, 66, 69} {80, 87, 89, 100, 103, 111 }
	{10, 12, 25, 26, 31}, {46, 49, 54, 59, 61, 65, 66, 69} {80, 89, 100, 103, 111 }, {87}

for *k*=4 (Fig. 9), the assignment of at least one load to the coherent group {87}(i.e., load 86) has been made (finding the minimum path between them) in order to avoid the collapse of the particular island. Fig. 10 illustrates the islanding solutions determined by the execution of the exact ICI algorithm for all the possible number of coherent groups. The

Figure 8. Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 118-Bus test system for *k*=3

Figure 9. Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 118-Bus test system for *k*=4

TABLE IV

EXACT ISLANDING SOLUTIONS FOR THE IEEE-118 BUS TEST SYSTEM

No. of Islands (<i>k</i>)	Cutset	Cut (MW)	Time (s)
	15-33, 19-34, 30-38, 24-70, 24-72	81.050	0.126
	15-33, 19-34, 30-38, 24-70, 24-72, 76-118, 75-77, 69-77, 68-81	229.402	0.214
	15-33, 19-34, 30-38, 24-70, 24-72, 76-118, 75-77, 69-77, 68-81, 85-86	246.574	0.319

information about the splitting strategies found, the values of the cuts and the execution times are presented in Table IV.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper an exact ICI algorithm based on a MILP formulation that directly determines an islanding solution with minimal power-flow disruption for any given number of islands is proposed. The constraints applied when satisfying this objective function deal with coherent generator groups and transmission line availability. Additionally, the algorithm allows the control of the size of islands and ensures the connectivity inside them. Since the MILP formulation allows the easy manipulation of its existing constraints, a preprocessing procedure is also developed for reducing the search space of the MILP. The objective of the preprocessing procedure is to find a tree for each island with minimum number of nodes, spanning to all generator nodes of its

Figure 7. Preprocessing procedure on IEEE 118-Bus test system for *k*=2

coherent group. The nodes that are included in these trees are directly assigned to their resulting island, ensuring the generator coherency. The effectiveness and the computational efficiency of the proposed ICI algorithm have been demonstrated under different system conditions.

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